

With American Library Association's year 1970 prediction on broad spectrum research results' effects, extending well beyond librarianship, on determining in large measure the future directions of library services and the nature of the profession itself¹, Busha's² (1981) argument on the necessity of transdisciplinary methodologies to study the many problems facing librarianship today, Frohmann's³ (1994) call for addressing librarianship dysfunctionalities and increasing anxiety of irrelevance and finally the urgent address to maintain currency with changing technological, social and pedagogical paradigms (Spink, 2012)⁴ resonating today stronglier than ever, the Third International Conference on Higher Education Advances (HEAd'17) hosted by the Faculty of Business Administration and Management of the Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain during 21-23 June 2017 presented a great moment of opportunity for HE professionals, from faculty and administrators to LIS experts and researchers in the field, to exchange findings, experience and viewpoints on student progress and HE organizational issues.

Holding high hopes for Conference contribution to

- helping overcome narrow-sighted domain-centric perceptions dominating LIS profession by opening up new perspectives to potential institutional units collaborations that could eventually be beneficial to all stakeholders,
- changing mindsets about student-centered environments, student-centered services, social pedagogy and informal group learning

we looked forward to the opening of the event where Prof. Josep Domènech, Chair of the Organizing Committee, after warmly welcoming delegates, briefly outlined the Conference objectives and introduced, in the heavily crowded Conference Hall, first keynote speaker, Michelle Morgan, Associate Professor and Associate Dean of Student Experience in the Faculty of Media and Communications at Bournemouth University, who in her opening presentation "Postgraduate Study- the next academic employability frontier", after taking the opportunity to congratulate the organizers for the variety of topics and innovative research presented every year, stressed the importance of student population data collection and the need to holistically address educational issues. She also commented on the changing landscape associated with postgraduate studies and the effort to bridge different stakeholders' expectations. Drawing from her recent Postgraduate Experience Project key findings, she highlighted students' demand for more personalized learning, recorded fairly low academic support service use, the rising importance of metrics in educational process evaluation and the short-sighted vision related to their collection and capitalization so far.

In the Q&A short session that followed, there was reference made once again to the growing number of postgraduate student populations that dictate more program flexibility and enhanced data collection, not to mention more support and personalized attention.

As the Conference was designed to address a wide variety of issues, program was deployed over 10 sections, each comprising of 3 to 4 parallel sessions, besides the highly motivational keynote addresses delivered by Professors Michelle Morgan, Piet Kommers, Utrecht University, and Javier Oliver, Universitat Politècnica de València, and articulated as figuring in the Appendix and revolving around major topics as illustrated in Table (1):

Concept	Occurrences
Innovation-related	10
Assessment, evaluation (of which 2 student-driven)	14
Feedback	5
Students' expectations	4
Impact-related	4
Students' perceptions	3
Teachers' perceptions	2
Achievement, outcomes	4

Table 1 HEAd'17 presentations' titles concept frequencies (<https://www.online-utility.org>)

From day one, we were emerged to the changing HE landscape characteristics where, as highlighted by Pr. Renata Clerici's presentation "Teachers' perceptions about their practices and needs for improvement: A qualitative research project at the University of Padova", student population lack of motivation, high heterogeneity, passive participation and irregular attendance among other critical issues, make even more pressing the demand for in-situ institution-based practices. According to her project, excellence is conceived by educators as a continuum of both internal and external factors with an emphasis on student motivation, mentoring and organizational development although there is still, as discussed in the Q&A session, senior faculty resistance to L&T developments.

During the same day, we had the opportunity to become familiar with various innovative research lines among which researchers' attempt to connect student perceptions surveys to lecturer effectiveness on student progress (DOCENTIA-UJI model) and Angela Siobhan Wright's new Tripartite Assessment inline with the rise of HIPs and Enquiry Based Learning, Prof. Marta Rojo's, University of Burgos, Project on active student participation in exam question bank preparation, and Dr. Lucille Mazo's (MacEwan University, Canada) research focusing instructor's learning style strong impact on teaching and lesson delivery, David Azcona's, (conference day II) Dublin City University research on predictive educational analytics data sources among which library attendance and book withdrawal, wifi geolocation analysis and personalized programming learning, Francesco Agrusti's, Roma Tre University, presentation on lexical analysis-based student critical thinking improvement assessment programs and Prof. Da-Fu Huang's outcomes assessment-related student alerts in Taiwanese Polytechnic Higher Education.

During the HEAd'17 Conference we also had the chance to appreciate research involving fluid and crystallized knowledge effects on student success predictions (Ipek Mete), the development of new lecture environments (Anja Pfenning, Berlin University of Applied Sciences), the rising importance of rethinking and capitalizing student activity data and the poor correlation between objective and subjective assessment (Robyn Maree Slattery, Monash University).

As librarianship research goals, objectives and methodologies are being reformulated under the new pedagogy scenarios that are prioritizing collaborative and project based learning as supportive to students against the discomfort of the hybrid third space (Babha, 2004 in Katja Davidoff and Carol Piñeiro's presentation) in developing a new understanding of their own and others' identities, attending HEAd'17 has been a mind-opener to transformational changes reshaping HE that every LIS professional should become aware of, critically engaging participants in a contextual framing reconceptualization through the eyes of Movers and Shakers of the field.

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HEAD'17 CONFERENCE REPORT

UPV, Spain

APPENDIX

	Wednesday 21	Thursday 22	Friday 23
9:00 - 10:30	Opening	5a. Entrepreneurship	9a. Assessment (III)
	Keynote I Prof. Michelle Morgan	5b. On-line Learning (II) 5c. Scientific and Research Education (I) 5d. Teacher Education (II)	9b. Competences (II) 9c. Scientific and Research Education (II)
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee break		
11:00 - 12:15	1a. Economics 1b. Emerging Technologies Practices 1c. On-line Learning (I) 1d. Teaching-Learning Process Perspectives	6a. Assessment (II) 6b. Engineering 6c. Planning and Organization (I) 6d. Student Engagement	10a. Competences (III) 10b. Gamification 10c. Multimedia 10d. Project-based Learning (II)
12:15 - 13:15	2a. Assessment (I) 2b. Health 2c. Innovative Teaching Methods (I)	Keynote II Prof. Piet Kommers	Keynote III Prof. Javier Oliver
13:15 - 14:30	Lunch		Closing
14:30 - 15:45	3a. Flipped Learning (I) 3b. Integration 3c. Social Media 3d. Student Feedback	7a. Computer-based Learning (I) 7b. Ethics and Culture (I) 7c. Flipped Learning (II) 7d. Project-based Learning (I)	
15:45 - 16:45	Poster Session (I)	Poster Session (II)	
16:45 - 18:15	4a. Competences (I) 4b. Linguistics 4c. Pedagogy 4d. Teacher Education (I)	8a. Computer-based Learning (II) 8b. Ethics and Culture (II) 8c. Innovative Teaching Methods (II) 8d. Planning and Organization (II)	